

TYPES OF MUSIC LESSONS

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Annotation: this article provides detailed information about music lessons, different forms and methods of conducting music lessons, types of music lessons and their analysis.

Keywords: lesson, music, type, method, teacher, interest, student, culture, community, listening, performance.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada musiqa darslari, musiqa darslarini o'tkazishda tangi shakllar va metodlar, musiqa darslarining turlari va ularning tahlili haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: dars, musiqa, tur, metod, o'qituvchi, qiziqish, o'quvchi, madaniyat, jamoa, tinglash, ijro.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлена подробная информация об уроках музыки, различных формах и методах проведения уроков музыки, видах уроков музыки и их анализе.

Ключевые слова: урок, музыка, вид, метод, учитель, интерес, ученик, культура, сообщество, слушание, исполнение.

The content of the lessons when the teacher is creating a music lesson not only to diversify, but also to diversify its structure. The lesson should not freeze in one mold. The teacher should approach his work and look for new forms and methods of conducting music lessons. Currently, music lessons can be divided into the following types.

1. Mixing.
2. Work on new materials
3. Returning the passed topics
4. Thematic. [1]

The type of lesson is determined by its purpose, content, and structure. Below we will touch on each of the lesson types. A blended lesson includes the three main activities of music education: group singing, listening to music, and music literacy. It is called blended because in this type of lesson, in addition to covering new material, the previous lessons are returned. If the material to be explained in the lesson is complex, it should be condensed and summarized in such a way as to relax the children's brains without straining them.

If the new material is not heavy, it can be given more, and during the return it is necessary to stop only on difficult areas. It should not be forgotten

that there are three sections in the music lesson, which are connected with each other and correctly distributed in terms of tasks. Therefore, if new material is covered in one activity, it is recommended to go back in the remaining activities. For example, if a new song is being learned in class, then the music literacy should be reviewed.

If the lesson continues the work on the song learned in the previous lessons, the teacher will pass a new topic in the section of music literacy possible usually, as a relaxing activity from listening to music is used. If the class is full of new, heavy material. It is known to children in order to entertain them while listening to music

It is desirable to return the deposit. Easy in class given the material, a new piece of music can be shown. There is also the problem of which type of activity to go through first in the lesson. This is due to many factors, and the options may be overwhelming in mixed classes with the same structure, but was characteristic for the structure of mixed-type music lessons. Some general principles are defined as follows:

1. The first half of the lesson is the most productive, because the children are too not tired and focused. That's why from which activity belongs in lesson planning for regardless of the new and complex material, the first lesson should be given in half.
2. It is difficult to relieve fatigue and boredom in class material with lighter, mental work practical training with, singing skillfully with other activities should be replaced.
3. To include singing, music literacy, listening to music need in elementary grades, in some cases, music literacy or listening to music cannot be included. But in all classes there must be a group singing activity.
4. The main activity during the lesson is singing as a group is considered.
5. As much as possible, the lesson should be started with singing. Because it is the situation organizes the child well and refreshes his spirit.
6. Singing according to the note and developing music listening 8-10 minutes should be reserved for exercises in each lesson.
7. Listening to music and repeating the song at the end of the lesson will be held.
8. It is necessary to repeat and strengthen the new topic taught in each lesson.

[2]

Based on these principles, the structure of the lesson can be structured according to the most used scheme below:

- a) singing as a team;

- b) musical literacy (singing according to a new theme and note);
 - c) continue singing;
 - g) listening to music (new work);
 - d) return the song learned in previous lessons;
- or
- a) singing;
 - b) learning a new song;
 - c) music literacy (repetition) exercises that increase musical learning, practical tasks, singing according to the note;
 - g) repeating the learned song;
 - d) listening to music (a new piece). [3]

In the lesson of working on new materials, the teacher works on new topics and works in all activities. When conducting such a lesson, the volume of new concepts that the teacher gives to children should not be too much. The presence of all three activities in the lesson allows the child to study peacefully without straining. It is known that the lesson was observed at such a time. It is very good to have a goal, which is all the activities of the lesson creates an opportunity to connect with each other. For example, one of the first lessons in the first grade is to learn register in music is dedicated.

After singing a little song, the teacher to the children sounds are different in terms of high-low, high, low, average explains the part. Bright contrast from listening to music children's understanding of pitch based on examples strengthened and defined. Then, the teacher is new poem in the process of teaching, he plays his melody in different registers and this to the children the song from the bird, from the elephants, if they know how to sing imagining the sounds coming out of your imagination he says, look. [4] So, analyzing the structure of the lesson, its three it can be seen that it consists of parts. All three parts of the lesson are strongly connected and connected to one goal due to the focus (registers), such a lesson with new materials even if it is full, it does not weigh on children.

The review lesson includes all three musical activities. It is devoted entirely to the review and reinforcement of the learning material already covered. Usually, the return lesson is held several times at the end of the quarter and at the end of the school year. If the return lessons are held at the end of the quarter, they will cover all the material of the section: group singing, music literacy and listening to music. Return lessons at the end of the school year can consist of two or even one part. For example, one lesson could be dedicated to

group singing only, and the second to music literacy and music listening, or the first lesson could be group singing and music literacy, and the second lesson to group. lib can take singing and playing music.

When organizing a lesson, it is necessary to choose the material in such a way that the most basic and necessary topics of the course are not missed. At the time of return, it is necessary to try to deepen and expand children's knowledge by giving them new facts and information. Only then will the return lessons be lively and interesting. When creating a plan for recovery lessons and a mixed type lesson, the teacher must combine all the musical activities of the lesson and focus on a single goal, taking into account the age and musical abilities of the child. Supervision work is also part of the return lessons. It is not necessary to control a lesson from the beginning to the end.

The lesson plan is drawn up as usual, only 10-15 minutes of the lesson can be allocated to performing control work on music literacy. Also, at the end of each quarter and at the end of the year, a full lesson is allocated to the supervision lesson. Control work can be verbal and written, written rhythmic or educational writing, determining the size of a musical example, placing a beat line in an example, creating intervals from one sound. [5] It is possible to conduct test control on all types of activities. In this case, it is necessary to make three or four answer options. The number of questions can be divided into tens, twelves, sixteens, then twenty and thirty.

Based on the curriculum, the questions should be simple and complex, suitable for the age of the child and the level of musical knowledge of the class. In a themed lesson, a specific, main topic is selected, and all musical activity materials are conducted around this topic. In this case, the subject of the lesson should be very diverse, that is, literary, musical, historical, modern, etc. For example, lessons can be devoted to Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Alisher Navai, Abu Nasr Farabi, folklore songs, women's holiday, memorial day, etc. The teacher should plan such lessons in a way that arouses children's enthusiasm, based on various evidence and interesting. Children love the thematic lesson, perceive it with great interest and enthusiasm. During the year, the thematic lesson can be held up to five or six times.

This type of lessons is more effective in upper grades, because it is possible to involve students who can independently prepare for the subject of the lesson and play musical instruments or perform vocal works in these classes.

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